

RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is strictly confidential and does not require the inclusion of respondent names.

Respondent No.: _____

Instructions: Please indicate your response by marking (X) in the box that best represents your answer.

SECTION I: RESPONDENT CHARACTERISTICS

1. **Gender**

a. Male

b. Female

2. **Age**

a. 18 – 29 years

b. 30 – 39 years

c. 40 – 49 years

d. Over 50 years

3. **Marital Status**

a. Married

b. Unmarried

4. **Education**

a. High School

b. Diploma

c. Bachelor's Degree

d. Postgraduate Degree

5. **Rank**

a. Senior Police Officer (Perwira Tinggi)

b. Middle-Ranking Officer (Perwira Menengah)

c. Junior Officer (Perwira Pertama)

d. Senior Non-Commissioned Officer (Bintara Tinggi)

e. Brigadier

f. Head Constable (Tamtama Kepala)

g. Constable (Tamtama)

SECTION II: RESEARCH ITEMS

Below are statements related to organizational performance, aspects of good governance (including distributive, procedural, and interactional justice), and effective organizational commitment. Please indicate your level of agreement with each statement by placing a check mark (√) in the corresponding box.

Scale:

1. **SD**: Strongly Disagree
2. **D**: Disagree
3. **SWD**: Somewhat Disagree
4. **A**: Agree
5. **SA**: Strongly Agree

Organizational Performance		SD	D	SWD	A	SA
1	The Aceh Regional Police has achieved its targeted goals.					
2	The Aceh Regional Police provides optimal services to the public.					
3	The institution is responsive to public complaints and demands.					
4	The organization completes its objectives on schedule.					

Good Governance		SD	D	SWD	A	SA
1	The Aceh Regional Police involves the public in policy formulation.					
2	The institution accepts input from the community.					
3	Officers who violate disciplinary rules are sanctioned.					
4	Leaders misusing authority are subject to firm action.					
5	Policies are made in the public's interest.					
6	Gender is a factor in the assignment of roles.					
7	Work implementation is based on effectiveness in achieving targets.					

8	The law is enforced equally for both staff and leadership.					
9	Work activities are carried out based on efficiency principles.					
10	Leadership consistently demonstrates a strategic vision for staff development.					

Organizational Citizenship Behavior		SD	D	SWD	A	SA
1	I follow the rules even when not being monitored.					
2	I am conscious about being honest in my work.					
3	I am willing to help colleagues in solving problems.					
4	I willingly assist those around me.					
5	I pay attention to changes within the organization.					
6	I actively contribute to improvements in the organization.					
7	I refrain from complaining about work.					
8	I maintain good interpersonal relationships.					
9	I remind colleagues about their actions to prevent problems.					

Competence		SD	D	SWD	A	SA
1	I consistently complete tasks on time.					
2	I am committed to continuous self-development.					
3	I have strong job-related knowledge.					
4	I possess the skills to perform assigned duties.					
5	I am highly motivated in my work.					

Integrity		SD	D	SWD	A	SA
1	I am honest in performing my duties.					
2	I speak the truth about situations as they are.					
3	I show wisdom when facing challenges.					
4	I take responsibility for my decisions and actions.					

Job Placement		SD	D	SWD	A	SA
1	I can perform a range of cognitive tasks such as reasoning and problem-solving.					
2	I possess the necessary proficiency for my job.					
3	I have specialized knowledge in a particular area.					

THANK YOU FOR YOUR PARTICIPATION